

Synthesis and Anthelmintic Activity of some New Isothiocyanates, Carbamates and *N'*-Furoylthioureas derived from 6-Amino-3-aryl/heteroaryl-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazines†

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Several new isothiocyanates (3a-k), carbamates (4a-k) and *N'*-furoylthioureas (5a-h) derived from 6-amino-3-aryl/heteroaryl-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazines have been synthesised and screened for their anthelmintic activity.

THE antiparasitic properties exhibited by a variety of isothiocyanates and carbamate derivatives have been very well documented¹. Furthermore, various *N,N'*-disubstituted-thioureas also have been reported to possess broad-spectrum anthelmintic activity². We recently reported³ the anthelmintic activity of certain isothiocyanates, carbamates and thioureas derived from 3-*N,N'*-disubstituted-amino/3-*N*-heterocycl-7-aminobenzoxazines. In view of the promising antihookworm activity exhibited by some of these compounds, we have now prepared, as part of our ongoing anthelmintic research programme⁴, some new isothiocyanates (3a-k), carbamates (4a-k) and *N'*-furoylthioureas (5a-h) derived from 3-aryl/heteroaryl-6-amino-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazines and evaluated for anthelmintic activity.

The key intermediates, 6-nitro-3-aryl/heteroaryl-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazines (1a-k) were prepared by the reaction of appropriately substituted bromomethyl ketones with 4-nitro-2-aminophenol either by refluxing in acetone in presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 (Method A) following the method described earlier⁵, or by carrying out the reaction under phase transfer catalytic conditions (PTC) in $CHCl_3$ -aqueous NaOH using tetrabutylammonium bromide as phase transfer catalyst (Method B). Reduction of the nitro-benzoxazines (1a-k) with hydrazinehydrate/Raney nickel in ethanol gave the corresponding aminoderivatives (2a-k). The targetted isothiocyanates (3a-k), carbamates (4a-k) and *N'*-furoylthioureas (5a-h) were prepared in good yields by treatment of the amino-derivatives with thiophosgene, ethylchloroformate and 2-furoylisothiocyanate, respectively (Scheme 1). The structures of compounds 3-5 (Table 1) were based on their elemental analyses and were further confirmed by ir and pmr spectra of the representative compounds.

1-5; Ar =
a; O_6H_5 e; $p-O_6H_4$ i; 2-Pyridinyl
b; $p-CH_3O_6H_4$ f; $p-BrO_6H_4$ j; 2-Thienyl
c; $p-CH_3COO_6H_4$ g; $p-CH_3COONHO_6H_4$ k; 4,5-Dibromo-
d; $p-FO_6H_4$ h; 2-Furyl thienyl

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were determined in glass capillaries using Gallenkamp melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Microanalyses were performed using a Hosli MK 101 microcombustion apparatus. Ir spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra were taken on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and chemical shifts expressed in δ -scale (ppm).

6-Nitro-3-*p*-fluorophenyl-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazine (1d):
Method B: A mixture of 4-nitro-2-aminophenol (1.54 g, 0.01 mol), *p*-fluorophenacylbromide (2.17 g, 0.01 mol), tetrabutylammonium bromide (0.32 g, 0.001 mol), sodium hydroxide (1.2 g, 0.03 mol), water (10 ml) and $CHCl_3$ (50 ml) was vigorously

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stirred at 50° for 12 h. The organic phase was separated and the aqueous solution extracted with fresh CHCl₃ (2 × 25 ml). The combined CHCl₃ layer was dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed under vacuum. The resulting solid was recrystallised from alcohol to furnish **1d** (2.17 g, 80%) as yellow crystalline solid, m.p. 162° (Found: C, 62.43; H, 3.74; N, 10.12. C₁₄H₉FN₂O₃ requires: C, 62.02; H, 3.32; N, 10.33%); δ (CDCl₃) 5.2 (2H, s, —CH₂— of oxazine ring), 6.7–7.3 (3H, m, Ar) and 7.9–8.2 (4H, m, Ar). Compounds **1b** (yield 72%, m.p. 180°); **1c** (70%, 150°) and **1e** (80%, 204°) were similarly prepared.

The following compounds were prepared according to Method A described earlier⁵: **1a** (55%, 157°), **1f** (62%, 187°), **1g** (57%, 194°), **1h** (50%, 158°), **1i** (45%, 169°), **1j** (47%, 192°) and **1k** (56%, 185°).

6-Amino-3-fluorophenyl-2H-1,4-benzoxazine (2d): To a solution of **1d** (2.71 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) and hydrazinehydrate (3 ml), a catalytic amount of Raney nickel was added and the reaction mixture heated on a steam-bath for 2 h. It was then filtered, solvent removed under vacuum and cooled and the resulting solid was filtered washed with water dried and recrystallised from alcohol to give pure **2d** (1.85 g, 77%), m.p. 137° (Found: C, 69.53; H, 4.3; N, 11.23. C₁₄H₁₁FN₂O requires: C, 69.71; H, 4.56; N, 11.62%); ν_{\max} 3 450 cm⁻¹ (NH₂); δ (acetone-d₆) 2.9 (2H, bs, NH₂), 5.0 (2H, s, —CH₂— of oxazine ring), 6.7, 7.3 and 8.1 (7H, 3m, Ar).

The following compounds were similarly prepared (yield, m.p.): **2a** (75%, 135°), **2b** (70%, 144°), **2c** (80%, 101°), **2e** (78%, 135°), **2f** (80%, 118°), **2g** (85%, 155°), **2h** (68%, 161°), **2i** (63%, 165°), **2j** (65%, 121°) and **2k** (69%, 152°).

6-Isothiocyanato-3-p-methoxyphenyl-2H-1,4-benzoxazine (3c): To a mixture of **2c** (1.27 g, 0.005 mol) and triethylamine (1.01 g, 0.007 mol) in acetone (100 ml) was added dropwise a solution of thiophosgene (0.6 g, 0.005 mol) in acetone (25 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature, concentrated in vacuum, the residue diluted with water (100 ml), the resulting solid filtered and recrystallised from acetone to give **3c** (1.2 g, 81%), m.p. 127° (Found: C, 64.54; H, 4.40; N, 9.62. C₁₆H₁₂N₂O₂S requires: C, 64.86; H, 4.05; N, 9.46%); ν_{\max} 2 100 cm⁻¹ (NCS); δ (CDCl₃) 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.7 (2H, s, —CH₂— of oxazine ring) and 6.8–7.5 (7H, m, Ar).

Compounds **3a, b** and **3d–k** were similarly prepared and listed in Table I.

Methyl-N-[3-(p-fluorophenyl)-2H-1,4-benzoxazin-6-yl]carbamate (4d): To a solution of **2d** (2.41 g, 0.01 mol) and NaHCO₃ (1.26 g, 0.015 mol) in aqueous acetone (50 ml) was added dropwise with stirring methyl chloroformate (1.04 g, 0.011 mol) at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h, the separated solid filtered and recrystallised from benzene to give pure **4d** (1.93 g,

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE ISOTHIOCYANATES (3), CARBAMATES (4) AND *N*-FUROYLTHIOUREAS (5)

Compd.* no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Nitrogen %	
				Found/ (Calcd.)	
3a	140	55	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ OS	10.82 (10.58)	
3b	146	57	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS	9.7 (10.07)	
3c	127	81	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.62 (9.46)	
3d	120	68	C ₁₁ H ₉ FN ₂ OS	9.54 (9.86)	
3e	145	75	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ OS	8.96 (9.32)	
3f	149	62	C ₁₁ H ₉ BrN ₂ OS	7.84 (8.12)	
3g	194	73	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.75 (13.00)	
3h	128	48	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.62 (10.94)	
3i	175	52	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OS	15.27 (15.73)	
3j	155	53	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₃	10.1 (10.29)	
3k	160	59	C ₁₁ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ OS	6.28 (6.51)	
4a	149	48	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	9.56 (9.93)	
4b	155	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	9.27 (9.46)	
4c	120	66	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	8.45 (8.97)	
4d	147	66	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O ₂	9.70 (9.33)	
4e	154	69	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂	8.37 (8.85)	
4f	162	64	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₂	7.29 (7.76)	
4g	178	67	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	12.67 (12.39)	
4h	165	55	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄	9.82 (10.29)	
4i	167	52	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄	14.67 (14.84)	
4j	137	57	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.48 (9.72)	
4k	180	71	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	5.87 (6.38)	
5a	182	57	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.43 (11.14)	
5b	135	52	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.53 (10.74)	
5c	127	64	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ S	9.87 (10.32)	
5d	189	49	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O ₂ S	10.26 (10.63)	
5e	187	53	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	10.47 (10.21)	
5f	192	45	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	9.12 (9.21)	
5g	141	61	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S	12.68 (12.90)	
5h	169	67	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ S	11.70 (11.44)	

* All compounds recrystallised from benzene-hexane; satisfactory C, H, analyses obtained.

66.5%) as crystalline solid, m.p. 147° (Found: C, 63.84; H, 4.58; N, 9.70. C₁₆H₁₃FN₂O₃ requires: C, 64.21; H, 4.35; N, 9.36%); ν_{\max} 1 720 cm⁻¹ (COOCH₃); δ (CDCl₃) 3.7 (3H, s, NHCOOCH₃),

5.1 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of oxazine ring), 6.9–8.2 (7H, m, Ar) and 8.5 (1H, bs, NH).

Compounds **4a–c** and **4e, f** were similarly prepared and listed in Table 1.

N-[3-Phenyl-2H-1,4-benzoxazin-6-yl]-N'-2-furoylthiourea (5a): To a refluxing solution of ammonium thiocyanate (0.84 g, 0.015 mol) in benzene (25 ml) was added dropwise a solution of 2-furoyl chloride (1.3 g, 0.01 mol) in benzene (10 ml) and refluxing continued for further 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, filtered and to the filtrate was added dropwise a solution of 6-amino-3-phenylbenzoxazine (**2a**; 2.24 g, 0.01 mol) in benzene (50 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h, concentrated to half its volume, cooled and the yellow solid obtained was filtered, washed with benzene and recrystallised from benzene—petroleum ether to give pure **5a** (2.16 g, 57.31%), m.p. 132° (Found: C, 64.04; H, 4.34; N, 11.43. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{S}$ requires: C, 63.66; H, 3.98; N, 11.14%); ν_{max} 1 680 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (DMSO- d_6) 5.2 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-$ of oxazine ring), 6.7–8.0 (11H, m, ArH and furan CH), 11.8 (1H, s, NH) and 12.9 (1H, s, NH).

Compounds **5b–h** were prepared similarly and listed in Table 1.

Anthelmintic activity: All the title compounds were tested in mice for their anthelmintic activity against *Nematospiroides dubius* at 4×500 mg/kg (p.o.), *Hymenolepis nana* at 1×500 mg/kg (p.o.) and *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis* in rats at 3×250 mg/kg (p.o.) according to reported procedures⁴. They were also tested for antihookworm activity

against *Ancylostoma ceylanicum* at a dose of 2×250 mg/kg (p.o.) in hamsters. Compound **3h** was found to possess a low order of antihookworm activity by causing 48% worm-load reduction of *A. ceylanicum*, while **4b** caused 100% worm-load reduction in 40% of the animals infected with *H. nana*. None of the compounds showed any noteworthy activity against *N. dubius* and *N. brasiliensis*.

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